

Analysis of Monthly Climatic Conditions Based on Moisture Availability Index: A Case Study in Mapalana, Low Country Wet Zone of Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Moisture Availability Index (MAI) is the ratio between the 75% probability precipitation based on the analysis of long-term precipitation records and estimated potential evapotranspiration. MAI is a prime factor for crop planning, especially in the tropics, which varies with time and space. The objectives of this study were to find out the nature of months according to the MIA in Mapalana, low country wet zone (LCWZ), Sri Lanka. Also, to find out the sowing period of crops, avoid water stress, and evaluate irrigation need every month of the year. Daily weather data was collected and converted to monthly average weather data to calculate MAI. Potential Evapotranspiration and Dependable Rain Fall were calculated for a long time (30 years). Moreover, the nature of the month was determined. For the Mapalana, LCWZ area, with the collected data set from the weather station situated in the Faculty of Agriculture, University of Ruhuna (19922022), MAI was calculated and the nature of the months at Mapalana area was determined. Results showed higher MAI, excessive moisture from October to November and lowest MAI, very deficient moisture from February to March. There is very deficient MAI in 2 months, moderately deficient in 5 months, somewhat deficient in 1 month, adequately deficient in 2 months and excessive moisture in 2 months. The crop will be normal if it receives moisture, varying from 0.3 to 1 of potential evapotranspiration commencing from germination to completion of the grain formation stage. In conclusion, according to the MAI, variations in the nature of months determine cropping season, crop potential, cropping pattern, land preparations and other management practices.

Keywords: *Low country wet zone, Mapalana, Moisture availability index, Nature of months, Potential evapotranspiration*